

**METFORMIN DEMONSTRATES EFFICACY IN OVERCOMING CISPLATIN
RESISTANCE WITHIN TRIPLE-NEGATIVE BREASTCANCER CELLS BY
SPECIFICALLY TARGETING RAD51**

Dr. Dhivya Prasath Palani Appan, Ann Jency A, Preethi Bala D, Priyadharsini R,

Subhalakshmi M

Swamy Vivekanandha College of Pharmacy

ABSTRACT:

Breast cancer, the most common disease in women worldwide, poses several difficulties, especially when it comes to triple-negative breast cancer (TNBC), which is defined by the lack of certain receptors. The RAD51 gene family, vital for DNA maintenance, is implicated in cancer, including TNBC. Cisplatin, a potent anticancer drug, often loses effectiveness due to resistance mechanisms. Metformin, a diabetes medication, has shown promise in breast cancer treatment. This study investigates their combined impact on TNBC. TNBC, constituting 12–17% of cases, lacks targeted therapies, posing challenges in recurrence prevention. TNBC subtyping remains a topic of exploration. TNBC predominantly affects younger women, displaying high invasiveness, short survival times, and early relapse. Risk factors include modifiable elements like drugs, physical activity, and diet, alongside non-modifiable factors like age and genetic history. Cisplatin, effective in various cancers, face limitations due to side effects and resistance. Metformin, with potential antitumor effects, is explored for its role in TNBC. The study delves into the molecular structures, mechanisms, and indications of cisplatin and metformin, highlighting their side effects. Chemoresistance, a challenge in cancer treatment, involves cancer stem cells. The study focuses on the chemoresistance of cisplatin and its role in TNBC. The combined treatment of cisplatin and metformin proves more effective in inhibiting TNBC cell viability and metastasis than cisplatin

alone. Metformin achieves this by suppressing RAD51, introducing a novel therapeutic approach for TNBC. In conclusion, the study suggests that metformin enhances cisplatin's anticancer efficacy in TNBC by inhibiting RAD51, providing a potential avenue for improved TNBC management.

KEY WORDS :

Breast cancer, Triple-negative breast cancer (TNBC), RAD51 gene family, Cisplatin resistance, Metformin, Chemoresistance, RAD51 suppression

INTRODUCTION :

In terms of newly reported cases, breast cancer ranks second globally and is the most frequent cancer among women. Several studies have illustrated the impact of lifestyle and environmental factors on the onset of breast cancer^[1]. Triple-negative breast cancer (TNBC) presents distinctive challenges in treatment due to the absence of human epidermal growth factor receptor 2 (HER2), progesterone receptor (PR), and estrogen receptor (ER)^[2]. The RAD51 gene and its family are crucial for maintaining DNA integrity because they are engaged in numerous processes, such as the replication stress response, meiosis, and double-strand break repair. In its role as an ATPase, RAD51 finds homologous DNA sequences and invades them to create a nucleoprotein filament on single-stranded DNA, allowing for precise and efficient DNA repair. Originating from ancestral gene duplications, paralogs of RAD51 have developed to modulate and augment the functions of

RAD51. Its relevance is highlighted by the connection between diseases like cancer and Fanconianaemia and the deregulation of RAD51 and its paralogs^[3]. Cisplatin (CDDP), a platinum derivative, is a potent drug widely employed for its efficacy in treating various cancers, including sarcomas, lymphomas, germ cell tumours, and carcinomas such as breast cancer^[4]. Metformin, a commonly prescribed biguanide for type 2 diabetes, has shown potential positive effects across different subtypes of breast cancer in both observational and preclinical investigations^[5]. In cases of metastatic breast cancer, systemic treatment methods like chemotherapy often prove ineffective, even though they are beneficial in addressing and curing breast tumours that are localized. The primary reasons for this ineffectiveness are the emergence of resistance to the chemotherapy agent and the establishment of inherent resistance to the treatment. The existence of cancer stem cells (CSCs) plays a pivotal role in both the natural and acquired resistance to chemotherapy^[6].

1. TNBC (TRIPLE-NEGATIVE BREAST CANCER) :

TNBC, a molecularly diverse form of breast cancer, is characterized by the absence of particular markers, setting it apart from other varieties. Hormone receptor immunohistochemistry (IHC) staining exhibiting less than 1% for progesterone and estrogen, together with the absence of HER2 gene amplification or HER2 protein overexpression, are characteristics. TNBC accounts for twelve to seventeen per cent of occurrences of breast cancer; it mainly affects younger women and is linked to a poor prognosis^[7]. Standard therapy is usually employed to address the lack of tailored therapeutic possibilities for TNBC, which often leads to recurrence^[8].

1.1 Types of TNBC :

There are six identifiable subtypes of TNBC: Immunomodulatory (IM), Mesenchymal (M), Luminal Androgen Receptor (LAR), Mesenchymal Stem-Like (MSL), Basal-like (BL1 and BL2),

and an Unidentified group (UNS). However, the practical relevance of this subtyping is still unclear from a clinical standpoint, thus more research is needed to clarify how it affects treatment decisions for TNBC^[9].

1.2 Epidemiology:

Triple-negative breast cancer comprises 15–25% of breast cancer cases and typically impacts women below the age of 40. TNBC patients experience a lower survival rate compared to those with other breast cancer subtypes, with 40% succumbing within the initial five years of diagnosis. High invasiveness in TNBC results in distant metastases in about 46% of patients. The median survival period following metastasis is a meagre 13.3 months, and the post-surgery recurrence rate is strikingly high at 25%. Metastases typically emerge in the third year after diagnosis, affecting the brain and visceral organs. TNBC patients relapse earlier, often between 19 and 40 months, as opposed to non-TNBC patients, who typically experience relapses between 35 and 67 months—the TNBC patients' death rate is within three^[10].

1.3 Risk Determinant:

Table 1. Changeable and Unchangeable risk factors of triple-negative breast cancer^[8]

CHANGEABLE	UNCHANGABLE
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Drugs	Lifetime
Physical Activity	Sex
Body Mass Index	Genetic Mutations
Alcohol Intake	Race/Ethnicity
Insufficient Vitamin Supplements	Genetic Background
Exposure to medications and chemicals	The density of breast tissue
Smoking	History of Radiation Therapy
Eating a processed food or diet	History of Breast Diseases
Complexities of TNBC Metastasis	

1.4 Pathogenesis:

The development of breast cancer encompasses various pathways, progressing from early stages to invasive tumours, with suggested models for initiation, transformation, and advancement. This session explains the aetiology and characteristics of metastatic TNBC with an emphasis on the triple-negative breast cancer predecessor^[11].

Predecessor:

According to the linear model, ER-positive ductal carcinoma in situ (DCIS), lobular neoplasia, atypical ductal hyperplasia, and flat epithelial atypia are considered non-obligate precursors for ER-positive cancers. These lesions can advance to high-grade conditions, resembling the potential

progression observed in low-grade invasive conditions like invasive tubular, lobular, and low-grade IDC-NSTs. The term "low-grade breast neoplasia family" was coined based on both histologic and genetic evidence, encompassing all low-grade ER-positive non-obligate predecessors and invasive carcinomas within its classification^[11].

About 7% of all DCIS lesions are high-grade ER-negative DCIS in TNBCs. These lesions share genetic developments, the prevalence of BRCA1 germline mutations, and intratumor genetic heterogeneity with synchronous IDC-NST, indicating that multiple clones within triple-negative DCIS may progress to invasive cancer^[11].

Through genomic and histological investigations, less advanced TNBC precursors such as microglandular adenosis (MGA) and atypical microglandular adenosis (AMGA) were discovered. These precursors show nearly the same patterns of copy number alterations (CNAs) and somatic genetic changes as high-grade TNBCs, indicating their potential as non-obligate precursors. Notably, due to common genetic changes and a propensity to evolve into high-grade triple-negative conditions, MGA, encompassing both atypia-free variations and those linked to invasive carcinoma, is recognized as a component of a low-grade triple-negative breast neoplasia family. Furthermore, there are similarities between acinic cell carcinoma and high-grade TNBCs, and there is a strong correlation between the two^[11].

Metastatic TNBC:

The likelihood for metastasis and sites of metastasis varies amongst several subtypes of TNBC. Compared to BL1, BL2, and M subtypes (32%, 33%, and 21%, respectively, $p = 0.02$), over half (47%) of patients with LAR TNBC subtype had lymph node dissemination. This subtype is a well-known predictor of lymph node metastasis. Additionally, there are differences in the incidence of

metastatic sites; the M subtype is more likely to develop lung metastases, while the LAR subtype is more likely to develop bone metastases^[11].

Between the primary and metastatic stages, there is fluctuation in the prevalence of TNBC subtypes. This discrepancy is predicted given that chemotherapy can treat BLIA, the most prevalent TNBC subtype. Compared to initial TNBCs, this subtype is less common in metastatic situations since many patients with it receive good treatment with current neoadjuvant chemotherapy^[11].

Metastatic triple-negative breast cancers exhibit genetic alterations similar to primary TNBCs, including TP53 mutations. However, ER-positive and LAR tumours, as well as M TNBCs to a lesser extent, are more prone to having mutations in PIK3CA, GATA3, CDH1, MAP3K1, PTEN, and PIK3R1. These findings suggest that LAR and M TNBC subtypes are likely to be more prevalent in metastatic cases due to their comparatively higher resistance to therapy when compared to BLIA. The evidence of the transformation of ER-positive or HER2-positive breast tumours in the original context to triple-negative disease in the metastatic situation offers an additional explanation for the disparities in somatic mutations between primary and metastatic TNBCs^[11].

Comparing metastatic triple-negative breast tumours to their primary counterparts, recent transcriptome investigations show that TILs and immune-activating genes are expressed at lower levels. This bolsters the theory that metastatic TNBCs might have a weaker immune response, reducing the fervour for immune checkpoint blockade when the disease is more advanced^[11].

1.5 Diagnosis:

A two-step procedure using imaging and Immunohistochemistry (IHC) is used to diagnose TNBC. Imaging methods, including mammograms, breast ultrasound, and MRI, are used to detect calcifications, growth, or masses indicative of breast cancer. Ultrasound is used when a lump is palpable but not visible on a mammogram, aiding in the differentiation between breast cysts and tumours. MRI is reserved for high-risk cases or to assess carcinoma severity due to its efficacy in early breast cancer detection. However, it cannot specify breast cancer types, only confirming their presence. Utilizing biomarkers like the Progesterone receptor, Estrogen receptor, and Human epidermal growth factor receptor 2, Immunohistochemistry (IHC) plays a vital role in determining the subtype of breast cancer, specifically HER2 status. The roughly 126 ASCO/CAP guidelines concentrate on improving the accuracy of IHC testing, interpreting results as positive for ER and PR if at least 1% of immunoreactive cancer cells are present, and advising HER2 confirmation by FISH following initial IHC confirmation to improve diagnostic precision and inform treatment decisions^[12].

1.6 Treatment:

Figure: 1 Treatment of TNBC^[10]

2. CISPLATIN:

FIGURE 2: Molecular structure of cisplatin^[13].

Cisplatin is an organometallic platinum complex that has two nearby amine and chlorine atoms. It is sometimes referred to as Cis-diammine-dichloro-platinum II. Its capacity to impede

Escherichia coli growth led to the discovery of its first known antibacterial qualities. It was discovered later that cisplatin has potent anti-neoplastic properties on tumour cells^[13].

2.1 Mechanism of action:

Figure 3: Cisplatin - mechanism of action^[13].

Through the formation of DNA adducts, such as intrastrand, interstrand, and monomeric cisplatin DNA cross-links, the technique aims to induce lethal effects on cancer cells. These cross-links initiate apoptosis, leading to the halting of the cell cycle at the S, G1, or G2-M phases. Cisplatin, as a component of the repair response, induces cell cycle arrest at the G2, S, or G1 phases. The major DNA adducts known as intrastrand crosslink adducts cause aberrant mitosis and, in the case of rapidly proliferating cancer cells, impair DNA replication, which in turn triggers apoptosis^[14].

2.2 Indications of cisplatin :

Cisplatin is widely recognised as a highly effective anticancer medication extensively utilized for treating solid tumours. Among its notable clinical applications, cisplatin is particularly effective in the treatment of lung cancer and is also employed for managing ovarian cancer. Clinical therapy for head and neck cancer, or head and neck squamous cell carcinoma (HNSCC), includes the administration of cisplatin. Additionally, cisplatin is employed as a chemotherapeutic agent for treating breast cancer. Moreover, cisplatin serves as a chemotherapy medication for breast cancer treatment^[14].

2.3 Side effects of cisplatin:

The utilization of cisplatin chemotherapy is frequently constrained due to significant side effects, notably nephrotoxicity, ototoxicity, neurotoxicity, and vomiting. The primary impediment to the extensive use of cisplatin is nephrotoxicity, which encompasses diverse mechanisms like oxidative stress, apoptosis, inflammation, and autophagy^[15].

In clinical settings, varying doses of cisplatin can result in distinct levels of nephrotoxicity. Individuals administered a single dose of cisplatin might experience reversible kidney damage, whereas substantial doses or repeated treatment courses could induce irreversible renal failure. Pharmacokinetic investigations further indicate that the primary contributors to nephrotoxicity are the extensive distribution of cisplatin and its prolonged accumulation in the kidney^[15].

3. METFORMIN:

FIGURE 4: Molecular structure of metformin[16]

For nearly a century, type 2 diabetes (T2D) has been effectively treated with metformin, a biguanide derivative. The anti-diabetic properties of guanidine were discovered in animals in 1918; however, its toxicity in clinical trials led to the search for safer alternatives. In the 1920s, scientists synthesized metformin (1,1-dimethyl biguanide hydrochloride), which emerged as the preferred option for T2D treatment due to its impressive ability to reduce plasma glucose levels. Over the years, research has revealed unexpected yet effective roles for metformin, particularly in influencing various types of cancer^[17].

3.1 Mechanism of action:

Figure 5: Metformin - mechanism of action^[18].

Metformin inhibits glucagon signalling in the liver by reducing adenylate cyclase activity, thereby suppressing gluconeogenesis. This occurs through the inhibition of protein kinase A (PKA)^[19].

3.2 Indications of metformin:

Metformin, the primary prescription for type 2 diabetes mellitus, has gained attention in recent years for more than its glucose-lowering properties. Various studies have provided evidence indicating the potential benefits of metformin, including anti-tumour effects, anti-ageing properties, cardiovascular protection, neuroprotection, and its consideration as an optional treatment for polycystic ovary syndrome^[20].

3.3 side effects of metformin:

The most typical side effects associated with metformin include nausea, a slight decrease in appetite, a metallic taste in the mouth, stomach pain, soft bowel movements, and diarrhoea. Additionally, metformin may hinder the absorption of vitamin B12. Although skin reactions are infrequent, metformin has the potential to induce lactic acidosis in individuals with normal kidney and liver functions, and in some cases, this condition can be fatal^[16].

4. CHEMORESISTANCE:

Overcoming chemotherapy resistance poses a considerable challenge in achieving effective cancer treatment, particularly in the context of metastasis, where it contributes to 90% of treatment failures^[21].

The emergence of chemoresistance is a recent and growing challenge in breast tumours. The prevalence of chemoresistance in breast tumours is heightened due to the aggressive nature of cancer cells. In breast cancers, YB-1 stabilization contributes to chemoresistance. The initiation of chemoresistance is facilitated by the translocation of CD24, which causes an increase in proliferation and a decrease in apoptosis^[22].

4.1 Chemoresistance of cisplatin:

CSCs (Cancer stem cells) constitute a small fraction within heterogeneous tumours and possess the capacity for self-renewal, being frequently implicated in the emergence of chemoresistance in cancer. The recurrence of metastasis following chemotherapy is believed to stem from the specific resistance of CSCs to therapy-induced apoptosis, enabling the tumour to re-establish itself post-treatment^[23]. Numerous intracellular mechanisms contribute to the evasion of the cytotoxic effects of therapeutics, particularly in association with CSCs. Activation of oncogenic

signalling pathways, the epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT), and processes that regulate drug accessibility all work together to create a phenotype that is extremely resistant to chemotherapy^[23].

5. Metformin and Cisplatin:

Cisplatin is frequently used to treat solid tumours such as ovarian and breast malignancies. It is reported to bind to the reactive N7 position of purine residues within Deoxyribonucleic acid. Rapidly dividing cancer cells experience breakage in their DNA double-strand caused by this interaction, which prevents further cell division and triggers apoptosis. Although cisplatin is initially useful in treating solid tumours, homologous recombination DNA repair mechanism activation eventually reduces cisplatin's anticancer efficacy. The development of resistance to this drug is attributed to the RecA homologous DNA repair recombinase protein known as RAD51. This protein forms a nucleoprotein filament on single-stranded DNA and is essential for the repair of cellular DNA. RAD51 plays a critical role in exchanging DNA strands with the intact homologous chromatid. Inhibiting this process should enhance the vulnerability of tumours to genotoxic drugs that cause DNA damage, like cisplatin^[6].

It was demonstrated that a 5 mm concentration of metformin suppressed the cisplatin-induced activation of extracellular signal-regulated kinase (ERK), leading to a decrease in phosphorylated ERK1/2 levels. Consequently, RAD51 expression was downregulated in triple-negative breast cancer (TNBC) cells, specifically Hs578T and MDA-MB-231. This process involved reducing the stability of the RAD51 protein, accompanied by an increase in degradation mediated by the 26S proteasome. Consequently, the synergy between metformin and cisplatin enhanced DNA damage, impeding the growth, migration, invasion, and metastasis of cells. The combined

administration of cisplatin and metformin suppressed the growth of tumour xenografts derived from the injection of 4T1 cells in a breast cancer mouse model (BALB/c animals). This inhibition was concurrent with a corresponding reduction in RAD51 levels^[6].

6. METFORMIN EXERTS BOTH DIRECT AND INDIRECT EFFECTS IN BREAST CANCER:

Figure 6: Direct and indirect effect of metformin[24].

Through its effects on angiogenesis, cell growth, proliferation, glucose metabolism, the transition from epithelial to mesenchymal tissue, the advancement of the cell cycle, DNA damage, and

inflammation, the antidiabetic biguanide metformin exhibits antitumor activity. Both an indirect (insulin-dependent) influence and a direct (insulin-independent) impact are responsible for these outcomes, which are mediated by AMPK activation. In the latter case, metformin decreases insulin levels, which lowers blood glucose levels by limiting gluconeogenesis and increasing the liver's production of glycogenolysis. Additionally, it improves muscle glycogenesis, lipogenesis, protein synthesis, and glucose utilization, concurrently decreasing the release of free fatty acids from adipose tissue and increasing the production of growth hormone^[24].

7. RAD51 GENE:

Many tumour forms, including breast cancer, show increased expression of RAD51. The increased expression of RAD51 does not stem from the amplification of the RAD51 gene per se; rather, it is associated with elevated transcription, decreased methylation, and/or enhanced stability of the protein. It has been suggested that RAD51 overexpression promotes aberrant recombination processes, which increase DNA damage in precancerous cells. Heterozygosity is lost and aneuploidy is produced by these abnormal recombination processes, which include chromosomal amplifications, deletions, and translocations. Ultimately, these incidents contribute to the growth of cancer and its metastasis to other bodily regions^[25].

8. BY INDUCING RAD51, METFORMIN IMPROVES CISPLATIN'S EFFICACY IN PREVENTING MIGRATION AND METASTASIS:

TNBC cells require RAD51 to proliferate and spread metastatically. To investigate whether RAD51 is responsible for the advantageous effects of metformin and cisplatin co-treatment, the investigation utilized either the overexpression or knockdown of RAD51. The study confirmed the

overexpression of RAD51-flag in MDA-MB-231 cells, leading to the reversal of the inhibition of migration and invasion in both MDA-MB-231 and Hs578T cells with the combined treatment. Notably, the introduction of RAD51 siRNA resulted in a significant reduction in RAD51 expression. However, it was demonstrated that the combination of cisplatin and metformin did not enhance invasion and migration in the presence of RAD51 downregulation. These findings strongly suggest that RAD51 plays a crucial role in the anticancer effects observed in metformin plus cisplatin therapy^[26].

9. CONCLUSION:

The concurrent use of cisplatin and metformin demonstrated a greater decline in both cell viability and metastatic outcomes in comparison to the use of cisplatin alone. By reducing RAD51 protein stability and increasing ubiquitination, metformin prevented the cisplatin-induced increase of RAD51. By suppressing RAD51 expression, metformin improves the anticancer efficacy of cisplatin and opens up a new therapeutic option for TNBC.

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